

Caves in the Skies: A sound cartography of Exoplanets

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Abstract

This paper presents a multidimensional sonification of exoplanetary data, developed in the Max/MSP environment and based on parameter mapping sonification (PMSon). Astrophysical parameters, such as surface temperature, habitability index, substellar–nadir delta, and ice fraction, were mapped onto perceivable and spatialized sonic properties, allowing for the exploration of differences between Cold, Hot, and potentially Habitable planets. The project integrates scientific data with timbral metaphors, generating an immersive soundscape that fosters both analytical insight and aesthetic engagement at the intersection between sound art and data representation. The methodology, aesthetic design, and future perspectives are discussed within the context of recent literature on sonification.

Keywords Sonification, Exoplanets, Parameter Mapping, Electroacoustic Composition, Data-driven Sound

1. Introduction

Sonification, defined as the transformation of data into non-verbal auditory signals, represents today an interdisciplinary field bridging science, technology, and the arts. As Kramer et al. (2010) point out, it enables the translation of information contained in datasets into perceptible relations in the acoustic domain, leveraging the human auditory system's remarkable ability to recognize

complex temporal patterns. This approach proves especially relevant for representing dynamic, multidimensional, or otherwise difficult-to-visualize phenomena, such as the study of extrasolar planets (exoplanets). Sonification is part of the broader field of Auditory Displays, which explores how the auditory system can function as the primary channel for communicating and transmitting information (Hermann, Hunt and Neuhoff 2011, 1). Examples include the sound of a Geiger counter or the pitch changes in monitoring devices in intensive care units.

"Sonification is clearly a subset of auditory display, but it is not clear, in the end, where the exact boundaries should be drawn" (Walker and Nees 2011). Within this broader field, Hermann (2008) defines sonification through four necessary conditions: sound must accurately reflect the objective properties of the input data; transformations must be systematic and well-defined; results must be reproducible; and the system must apply to different datasets. From this perspective, sonification implies a systematic mapping from data dimensions to acoustic dimensions.

The technique described above can be configured through an algorithm, i.e., a set of operations that transform input data into a predetermined result (output) uniquely and finitely, making the solution the same for all questions belonging to the same class. In the music field, programming languages such as MaxMSP, CSound, and SuperCollider enable the creation of algorithms with various purposes (e.g., synthesis, sound transformation, and spatialization, to name a few).

For taxonomic purposes, Walter and Nees (2011) distinguish between Functions and Techniques of sonification. We consider this a helpful approach even if,

as the authors point out, "However, these descriptions should not be taken to imply that clear-cut boundaries and distinctions are always possible to draw or agree upon, nor are they crucial to the creation of a successful display". Among the Functions found by the authors (such as Alerting Functions¹, Status and progress indicating functions², and Data exploration functions³) there is Arts and Entertainment, which, over the last few decades, has established sonification itself not only as an analytical tool for the representation of scientific data, but also as an expressive means aimed at aesthetically exploring complex and stratified information.

The Techniques (Audification⁴, Earcons⁵, Auditory Icons⁶, and Model-Based Sonification⁷) include Parameter Mapping Sonification (PMSon), which "...involves the association of information with auditory parameters for data display. Since sound is inherently multidimensional, PMSon is – at least in principle – particularly well suited for displaying multivariate data." (Berger and Grond 2011, 365).

This work proposes a multidimensional sonification of exoplanetary data, which is used to generate and modulate perceptible sound characteristics according to the principles of Parameter Mapping Sonification. This technique involves transforming the input data range to the output data range. In addition, the work adopts an approach inspired by spatial sonification, as described by Nasir and Roberts (2007), considering not only the auditory representation of data but also their distribution in acoustic Space. The decision to spatialize the planets in semantic categories (cold, hot, and habitable) and to associate specific trajectories, resonances, and sound textures has enabled the creation of an immersive soundscape, where scientific elements are intertwined with perceptual and symbolic suggestions.

This project is therefore characterized by its dual nature: on the one hand, it represents a concrete example of sound transposition of scientific data; on the other, it explores artistic and narrative possibilities typical of contemporary sound art. This theoretical introduction aims to provide the framework that guides and justifies the choices made in mapping and sound design, which will be explored in depth in the following sections.

¹ "Alerting functions: *Alerts and notifications* refer to sounds used to indicate that something has occurred, or is about to occur, or that the listener should immediately attend to something in the environment" (Walker and Nees 2011, 13).

² "The current or ongoing status of a system or process often needs to be presented to the human listener...." (Walker and Nees 2011, 14) such as blood pressure in a hospital environment.

³ "... and are usually intended to encode and convey information about an entire data set or relevant aspects of the data set". (Walker and Nees 2011, 14). The Model-based sonification techniques is an example.

⁴ "Audification is a technique of making sense of data by interpreting any kind of one-dimensional signal (or of a two-dimensional signal-like data set) as amplitude over time and playing it back on a loudspeaker for the purpose of listening..... audification is essentially a continuous, non-digital interpretation of data sets....". (Dombois and Eckel 2011, 301) "In the case of audification, we therefore try to minimize the transformations of data prior to listening in order to be able to perceive them as far as possible in their "raw" state". (Dombois and Eckel 2011, 307)

This sonification was created for the Science/Art multimedia project *Caves in the Skies*, based on scientific data from Dra Erica Bisesi (Bisesi et al. 2025) and exported as an audio file intended for integration into an audiovisual context; the sound component therefore does not have a purely ancillary function, but constitutes a structural element of the narrative and perceptual discourse of the video, which included nine exoplanets (out of a total of twenty-two).

Taking into account the artistic purpose and the expected format of the final result, the procedure was carried out in two steps: on the one hand, the design of an algorithm for the mapping of the data; on the other hand, the "composition" of the musical path according to the video. The exoplanets studied during the research are 22; the algorithm mapping is unique, i.e., the input data for each exoplanet produces a predictable and reproducible sound result (output). For musical reasons, some random variations have been introduced into the algorithm regarding the use of synthetic samples generated with specialized algorithms (see the following section). The sonification of the video is only one of the possible outcomes. In addition to creating more extensive soundtracks with all the data (the 22 exoplanets), the algorithm can be used in real-time (as live electronics) or incorporated into an installation through interface modification. In this case, user interactions can also be envisaged, bringing the result closer to the Model-based typology.

This paper situates the artistic project *Caves in the Skies* within this framework, applying parameter mapping sonification (PMSon) to astrophysical data to construct an immersive sound cartography of exoplanets.

2. Methodology

The project adopts a multidimensional sonification approach based on parameter mapping sonification (PMSon) (Berger and Grond 2011). Exoplanetary datasets considered include both quantitative parameters (surface temperature, ice fraction, habitability index) and ordinal

⁵ "...Earcons can be thought of as short, structured musical messages, where different musical properties of sound are associated with different parameters of the data being communicated. The key difference between these and Auditory Icons is that there is no assumption of an existing relationship between the sound and the information that it represents. This relationship must, at least initially, be learned". (Brewster and Gookin 2011,339)

⁶ "Auditory icons aim to provide an intuitive linkage between the metaphorical model worlds of computer applications by sonically representing objects and events in applications, using sounds that are likely to be familiar to users from their everyday life". (Brazil and Fernstrom 2011, 326)

⁷ "Parameter Mapping Sonification (PMSon) involves the association of information with auditory parameters for the purpose of data display. Since sound is inherently multidimensional, PMSon is – at least in principle – particularly well suited for displaying multivariate data." (Berger and Grond, 2011, 365)

categories (cold, hot, habitable). These were mapped onto acoustic and spatial parameters, after rescaling and normalization. The qualitative dataset groups the planets into three categories, with quantitative variables associated with each.

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Planets	Ice-fraction (0-1)	T-surf-PlaSim (K)	ΔT substellar-nadir	Habitability (0-1)
2	Cold	1	186.78 - 203.73	59.52 - 64.63	0
3	Hot	0	296.86 - 330.07	15.12 - 40.55	0.6 - 0.957
4	Habitable	0.7 - 0.83	218.19 - 257.07	55.84 - 97.78	0.099 - 0.326

Figure 1

The Table presents the data considered by the scientific research carried out by Murante et al. (2025) and Bisesi et al. (2025) in relation to the analysis of exoplanet habitability.

The data presented as interval (see T surf-PlaSim for example) are values extrapolated from the data set reported by Bisesi et al. (2025) and presented in this paper in a synthetic way in the Table.

The Hot/Cold/Habitable dataset is ordinal since it presents ordered and qualitatively differentiated categories. Data classification was carried out according to Barras (1997, 2), who states, "The design of an appropriate representation requires a description of the information to be represented."

Ice fraction indicates the amount of ice on the planet, scaled between 0 and 1. Cold planets, as expected, have a value of 1, while hot planets have a value of 0. The range between 0.7 and 0.83 of the habitable planets indicates that ice is present beyond the habitable zone in varying proportions. The range of 0.7 to 0.83 is extrapolated from the maximum and minimum values obtained from the research data.

The T-surf PlaSim (Planet Simulator) provides surface temperature values in Kelvin. The acronym PlaSim (Planet Simulator) is an Intermediate Complexity Model used for climate simulations of Earth and other planets in the solar system. An intermediate-complexity model or MIC (Model of Intermediate Complexity) balances the complexity of the model with computational capabilities, delivering acceptable results without requiring excessive resources.

The Habitability index reflects the likelihood of liquid Water at surface temperatures between 0° and 50°C, scaled between 0 and 1 (Bisesi et al., 2025).

The ΔT substellar–nadir index indicates the presence and size of habitable zones; the higher the index, the higher the Habitability. However, this is true only in the category of Habitable planets, because even though Cold and Hot

planets may show a higher Habitability Index (measured in terms of the presence of Water, an essential element for Habitability), their physical parameters, however, are not compatible with environmental conditions favorable for Life. Consequently, as can be seen in the Table, it is evident that Exoplanets considered Habitable do not necessarily have a higher Habitability Index than Hot Exoplanets and, for the same reason, only for Habitable, the higher the ΔT substellar–nadir index, the higher the Habitability (as in these planets the zones with Water are neither frozen nor boiling).

As a result, the mapping cannot follow a linear path within the three ordinal categories if a perceptual match is to be achieved. The directly proportional mapping, therefore, must be carried out within the Habitable category and is critical in distinguishing Habitability within the 'habitable' category.

The sonification system was implemented in Max/MSP, utilizing sound generation modules (noise, state-variable filters, and Frequency Modulation synthesis) and spatialization modules (via the IRCAM Spat5 library) to create dynamic trajectories within the virtual Space. In addition to parametric synthesis, an archive of sound samples (both concrete and synthetic) was employed, designed to represent the three planetary categories metaphorically.

The synthetic samples were created using the Sound Design Toolkit⁸, an open-source library within the Max MSP environment, which features algorithms for synthesis, processing, and data analysis. This toolkit is designed to simulate acoustic phenomena of both natural and non-natural worlds, encompassing categories such as Solids, Gases, Liquids, and Machines.

	A	B	C	D
1	Planets	Solids	Gas	Liquids
2	Cold	Friction Impact Scraping		
3	Hot		Windflow Windcavity	
4	Habitable			Bubble Fluidflow

Figure 2

The use of samples that recall the natural world appeals to the concept of source bonding (Smalley 1997) and the principle of Gestalt Past Experience. In this way, the evocative power of sonification is strengthened, aiming to acoustically represent a given dataset and make the

⁸ The Sound Design Toolkit (SDT) package per MaxMsp è stato sviluppato da Stefano Delle Monache, Stefano Baldan, Stefano Papetti, Marco Tiraboschi, Davide Rocchesso. Progetti europei: SOB (2001–2003, <http://www.soundobject.org/>), CLOSED (2006–2009, <http://closed.ircam.fr>), NIW (2008–2011,

<http://www.soundobject.org/niw/>), SkAT-VG (2014–2016, <http://www.skatvg.eu>). Zurich University of the Arts, Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology (ICST). <https://www.zhdk.ch/en/research/icst>

changes in one dimension perceptible in another.

"Parameter mapping represents changes in some data dimension with changes in an acoustic dimension to produce a sonification" (Walker and Nees 2011, 16)

3. Data Mapping Design

The mapping followed perceptually intuitive principles. However, the quantitative data have been indexed according to the order of the categories —Cold, Hot, and Habitable—to create a consistent narrative path. In all cases, the original dataset has been resized to align the ranges of the original variables with those of the sound variables.

"In order for parameter mapping to be used in a sonification, the dimensionality of the data must be constrained such that a perceivable display is feasible, thus parameter mapping tends to result in a lower-dimensional display than the model-based approaches discussed below". Walker and Nees 2011).

Surface temperature was mapped to filter cut-off frequency and FM carrier frequency, creating a direct proportionality between thermal energy and sonic frequency. Lower temperatures corresponded to darker timbres and lower frequencies, while higher temperatures yielded brighter timbres and higher frequencies, spanning the range of 100–6000 Hz. Although the range of frequencies audible to human perception is between 20 Hz and 20000 Hz, the maximum sensitivity is concentrated between 2000 Hz and 4000 Hz.

In the case of the Cold and Hot planets, the Temperature has also been mapped for the Q factor of the Filter (Resonance). Cold planets have a low Q with a wide bandwidth, while Hot planets have a high Q with a narrow bandwidth. The total range of Q (0 to 1) has been divided into two segments: 0 to 0.5 for Cold and Warm, and 0.5 to 1 for Habitable. From a perceptual point of view, this means that the Habitable planets will have a higher Resonance Q than the others and a clearer perception of Pitch. The Q factor of the filter in the case of Habitable is mapped as a function of the substellar-nadir ΔT index, meaning that the more habitable a planet is, the narrower the filter band will be.

Notice that this index also modulates the FM/SVG filter ratio in Habitable planets.

The habitability index itself determined the balance between noise-based and harmonic content: Cold planets were dominated by noise, Hot planets by a mixture, while Habitable planets combined spectral richness and harmonic clarity, with the index also controlling FM partials.

Ice fraction determines filter mode: low-pass for Cold planets (ice-fraction=1), high-pass for Hot planets (ice-fraction=0), and band-pass/notch modes for Habitable planets (intermediate values).

Ordinal categories further shaped duration, with Cold planets producing long sounds (up to 10s), hot planets

shorter ones, and habitable planets intermediate durations. Sounds with low frequencies have a longer wavelength, which means that the distance between two corresponding peaks is greater than for a sound with a higher frequency. In other words, a sound with a low frequency needs more time to complete a full cycle (period). The wavelength is inversely proportional to the period. It is therefore intuitive to associate a low sound with a longer duration, and these acoustical facts support the mapping.

Spatial trajectories were dynamically assigned using the IRCAM Spat5 library, with amplitude and radius proportional to duration. The library includes 63 types of spatial trajectories, which were triggered randomly. Cold planets were mapped to broad, slow trajectories, while Hot planets had narrow, rapid ones; Habitable planets were mapped to intermediate orbits. This is a metaphoric reference to the planet's position in the Solar System. The musical Space, as a compositional parameter, offers a wide range of further possibilities. The spatial parameters of the source (width, distance, position, depth, first reflections) and of the environment (global reverberation) can create real virtual spaces with convergences or divergences related to the Auditory Spatial Schemata (Kendall 2011), enriching the narrative and metaphorical possibilities to be used in subsequent applications of the present sonification.

Audio Samples

Figure 2 illustrates the type of association established between the Solids, Gases, and Liquids types with the Cold, Hot, and Habitable categories. Taking into account that the state of matter tends to solidify with the lowering of temperatures, the association between Solids-Cold (evokes immobility and rigidity) and Gas-Hot (dynamism and volatility) is immediate and natural. From a biological point of view, Life (as we know it) is associated with Water; therefore, the liquid-habitability association is also direct and intuitive.

The frequency of the samples varies as a function of temperature, which favors a more pronounced perceptual differentiation between the three categories. Each planet is thus represented by a unique and dynamic combination of frequencies, timbres, resonances, duration, and trajectory in acoustic Space, consistent with scientific data and enriched with perceptual and aesthetic metaphors.

4. Results and Discussion

The challenge with multidimensional sonification is translating heterogeneous parameters into distinguishable aural perceptions. The primary risk in these cases is that manipulating multiple sound parameters simultaneously increases the likelihood of interference and reduces the readability of the sound message (Walker and Nees 2011). To address this issue, the project adopted a semi-hierarchical approach, where global parameters (ordinal

categories) influence duration and spatialization. "... nominal/categorical data types... should be represented by categorically changing acoustic variables, such as timbre". (Walker and Nees 2011). Walker emphasizes the importance of data type in influencing the type of mapping, placing his thinking alongside Barrass's. In *Caves in the Skies*, the order of the nominal categories determines the narrative path of sonification that takes place from the non-habitable to the most habitable planets. Quantitative and continuous parameters, such as temperature (a ratio scale⁹) and habitability, on the other hand, are mapped onto the frequency and cutoff of the filter, as well as the harmonic spectrum-to-noise ratio. Specific parameters, such as nadir and ice fraction, modulate characteristics like resonance and filter type. This approach provided perceptual clarity while maintaining scientific fidelity.

The use of sound samples ("solids", "gases", "liquids") has added a metaphorical dimension that goes beyond the mere numerical representation. This is a deliberate choice that aligns with the literature on artistic sonification: sound can become a tool to evoke images, suggestions, and narratives that enrich the listening experience and foster an emotional connection with the data.

"First-order sonification is the direct linkage process between the data itself and some technique for rendering it in a sound space.... The second order offers an intermediary set of conceptual frames that allow for parameter-driven repetition and large-scale form creation from the statistics and grouping choices made when handling a given dataset.... This can give the designer an option for more culturally bound decisions that can frame the output in larger musically formal structures" (Grisham-Lancaster 2011).

From a compositional point of view, sonification can extend beyond the mere transposition of data from one dimension to another, ultimately achieving formal macro control over the sound result. The metaphors that associate rigidity (friction, scraping) with the Cold planets or mobility and instability (windflow, windcavity) with the Hot planets can be nothing more than the starting point of a wide-ranging compositional elaboration. In this way, a scientific dataset can be transformed into an immersive sound landscape, where data and sensory perception merge.

Another vital reflection concerns the decision to spatialize the planets, not only to enhance the perception of the categories but also to create an immersive experience that suggests the three-dimensional nature of the planetary system. As Nasir and Roberts (2007) observe, spatiality in the sound domain is less precise than visual representation, but it can still offer added perceptual value if used with clear criteria.

From the spatial point of view, the movement of sound

sources is one of the most relevant cognitive perceptions. For this reason, the type, speed, and amplitude of the trajectories have been taken into consideration to characterize the ordinal categories of Exoplanets. The choices made on this account have allowed us to suggest a "sound map" of planetary systems that evolves dynamically in acoustic Space. However, the approach adopted has some limitations, as some mappings may not be fully grasped due in part to information overload: the integration of many sound dimensions can generate perceptual complexity.

5. Conclusions

The Exoplanet Sonification Project, *Caves in the Skies*, aims to integrate rigorous data mapping with artistic sensitivity. By translating astrophysical data into perceivable sonic parameters, it transforms scientific information into a narrative and aesthetic soundscape. The project thus bridges scientific analysis and artistic creation, situating itself within contemporary practices of data-driven music and sound art (Bonet, 2019), with a specific focus on two fundamental dimensions. On the one hand, information fidelity, i.e., maintaining consistency between the original scientific data and their acoustic translation; on the other hand, perceptual and aesthetic quality that ensures that the listening experience is not only informative, but also sensorially stimulating and artistically coherent.

Sonification can become a tool not only for the analysis and representation of scientific data, but also for exploring new forms of listening and sensitive understanding of complex phenomena. It also opens up interesting prospects, including real-time implementations, live electronic versions, interactive installations, and audiovisual expansions, aligning with multimodal research directions (Curtis Roads et al., 2015), which could further expand the possibilities of communication and expression. A more careful aesthetic attention is also evident in NASA's Sonification project, which involves collaborations between scientists and musicians. An example of this is the Universe of Sounds project, the result of the partnership between NASA (Chandra X-ray Center) and System Sounds.

"The human element in the creation of these works is much more present, and specific compositional choices are used to craft a work of art out of the given data" (Cotturone 2025).

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⁹ The *ratio scale*, such as the Kelvin scale, is a quantitative scale that has a true 0 point (absolute zero) and allows direct comparison (e.g., 300 K is

twice as fast as 150 K). Absolute zero represents the absence of movement of the particles, i.e. the absence of energy.

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